

Ferrion Theory and the \mathcal{PT} -Symmetric Extension of Tachyon Dynamics

Gabriel De Jesus Sanchez Ferra
gabrielsanchezferra@gmail.com

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Abstract

It is often claimed that nothing in the universe can exceed the speed of light; at best, a massless particle can barely match it. But this oft-repeated claim has not been free from questioning. In 1962, Bilaniuk, Deshpande, and Sudarshan proposed a different view in an article published in the American Journal of Physics (30, 718). Years later, Bilaniuk and Sudarshan returned to the subject in a particularly clear and accessible text that appeared in Physics Today (22, 43; 1969). Tachyons are particles that hypothetically travel faster than light. Their existence has not been experimentally proven, but is predicted in theoretical formulations. Tachyons are characterized by having an imaginary mass. One of their properties that intrigues or attracts the attention of those who study them is the fact that they could travel backward in time and break the principle of causality, making it a very interesting area to study. Furthermore, we introduce the Ferrion, a hypothetical \mathcal{PT} -symmetric particle that offers an alternative framework for superluminal propagation without an imaginary mass, and explore its stabilization via a coupling to a Higgs field.

Index Terms- Superluminal particles, tachyons, special relativity, imaginary mass, \mathcal{PT} symmetry, Ferrion.

1 INTRODUCTION

In special relativity, nothing with mass can reach exactly the speed of light, because to do so would require infinite energy and therefore infinite momentum. Therefore, if something is slower than light, it will always be slower, and if something is faster than light, it will always be faster. Einstein discovered that speeds do not add up like normal numbers. Suppose you are traveling at $0.8c$ and an object in front of you is traveling at $0.8c$. You will not see it traveling at $1.6c$, since the relativistic formula always gives a value less than c so two observers in motion will never see anything cross the speed of light barrier. This means that if you see an object with a speed less than c , all observers will also always see it with a speed $< c$. Similarly, if you hypothetically see a tachyon with $v > c$, all observers will also see it with $v > c$ (although how much may vary).

Thus, particles can be classified into two different groups: particles with superluminal velocities (tachyons) and particles with subluminal velocities. If tachyons existed, their behavior would be very strange compared to normal matter.

Let's work in dimensions $1 + 1$ one spatial dimension (momentum) and one temporal dimension (energy). The lines

$$E = +pc, \quad \text{and} \quad E = -pc, \quad (1.1)$$

are the axes of the cone of light in the plane (p, E) . Every point on these lines satisfies

$$E^2 - p^2c^2 = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

(massless particles, luxons). The lines divide the plane into four regions: Up and down: timelike regions where $|E| > pc$ Left and right: spacelike regions where $|E| < pc$. The relativistic dispersion relation for particles with mass (tardyon/bradyon) is represented as follows:

$$E^2 - \mathbf{p}^2c^2 = m^2c^4, \quad (1.3)$$

with mass $m > 0$. For a given mass m , this equation represents a hyperbola whose branches lie in timelike regions (for example, the upper branch passes through $(p, E) = (0, mc^2)$). If we take $E = +\sqrt{p^2c^2 + m^2c^4}$ we obtain the upper branch (positive energy) where the real particle is physically and classically located. On the other hand, if $m = 0$ (luxon), the hyperbola collapses into the straight lines $E = \pm pc$ so the particle will move

exactly on the light cone (it travels at $v = c$). The equation $E^2 - p^2c^2 = m^2c^4$ allows m^2 to be negative. That is, if $m = iM$ is defined with M real, then $m^2 = -M^2$ and the relationship is rewritten as

$$p^2c^2 - E^2 = M^2c^4 \quad \text{or} \quad E^2 - p^2c^2 = -M^2c^4. \quad (1.4)$$

This is another hyperbola, but now its branches "live" in the spacelike region: $|E| < |p|c$. For these points, the deduced velocity (approximately $v = \frac{pc^2}{E}$) would be greater than c ($v > c$). In the relativistic formula

$$E = \frac{mc^2}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}} \quad (1.5)$$

if m is imaginary and $v > c$ the expression becomes real: that is the mathematical idea that suggested the possibility of particles with $v > c$. However, tachyons cause many conceptual problems (causality, instabilities), which is why they are not part of the set of particles observed in standard physical theory.

For tachyons, m^2 is negative, so m is imaginary. This makes their energy-momentum curves hyperbolic in the spatial region, not in the temporal region. If a tachyon loses energy E , its momentum p increases, and therefore it accelerates, that is,

1) Less energy \rightarrow faster, 2) Zero energy \rightarrow infinite speed ("transcendent" state).

If a tachyon had an electric charge while traveling faster than light, it would produce Cherenkov radiation, like a supersonic electron in a medium. By emitting Cherenkov radiation, it would lose energy, but losing energy would accelerate it further, thus creating an unstable chain reaction that would release infinite energy. Therefore, it is not possible to construct consistent theories with charged tachyons or strong interactions. The only "sensible" theories involve free tachyons (without interaction).

2 RELATIVISTIC THEORY OF A PARTICLE

Events are governed by four coordinates: x, y, z and time, i.e., a four-dimensional space. Rotations, on the other hand, can be broken down into six specific rotations in the xy, xz, zy, tx, ty, tz planes. On the other hand, normal rotations (such as rotating about the \mathbf{z} -axis) occur in planes such as xy, xz, yz . Rotations can also be performed in space-time, but involving time tx, ty, tz , where a rotation in the tx plane is precisely a Lorentz transformation. Normal rotation uses trigonometric functions $\cos\theta$ and $\sin\theta$ but in relativity, since time behaves differently from space, hyperbolic functions $\cosh\phi$ and $\sinh\phi$ are used. The base transformation is then expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= x \cosh\phi + ct \sinh\phi, \\ ct' &= x \sinh\phi + ct \cosh\phi. \end{aligned} \quad (1.6)$$

which is equivalent to a rotation, only of the "hyperbolic" type.

It should be noted that ϕ represents the hyperbolic angle associated with the velocity that satisfies the following

$$\tanh\phi = \frac{V}{c}. \quad (1.7)$$

and using hyperbolic identities, it can be shown that

$$\begin{aligned} \cosh\phi &= \gamma, \\ \sinh\phi &= \gamma \frac{V}{c}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.8)$$

If we substitute the values of $\cosh\phi$ and $\sinh\phi$ into the initial equations, the formulas are recovered $x' = \gamma(x + Vt)$, $t' = \gamma(t + Vx/c^2)$ and $y' = y$, $z' = z$. These are the Lorentz transformations.

In relativity, combining time and space becomes "simpler" if four-component objects called quadrivectors are used

$$x^\mu = (ct, x, y, z), \quad (1.9)$$

when the index is above, they are contravariant x^μ and when the index is below, they are covariant x_μ . The fundamental tensor is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} g^{00} &= 1, \\ g^{11} &= g^{22} = g^{33} = -1, \\ g^{\mu\nu} &= 0 \quad \text{for} \quad \mu \neq \nu. \end{aligned} \quad (1.10)$$

In special relativity, the Minkowski metric tensor can be expressed as a diagonal matrix:

$$g^{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.11)$$

Note that in this space $g^{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu}$. This tensor allows us to relate the covariant and contravariant components of a four-vector through:

$$x^\mu = g^{\mu\nu} x_\nu \quad (1.12)$$

The scalar product that remains invariant under Lorentz transformations for two vectors a_μ and b_μ is:

$$a \cdot b = a_0 b_0 - a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2 - a_3 b_3 = a^\mu b_\mu. \quad (1.13)$$

Using Einstein's notation for summation over repeated indices. If we consider two infinitesimally separated events in spacetime, the fundamental quantity that characterizes their separation is the space-time interval. in spacetime is ds and since ds must be the same for all (inertial) observers, it must be invariant under Lorentz transformations and ordinary rotations, that is

$$ds^2 = dx^\mu dx_\mu = c^2 dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2. \quad (1.14)$$

With this definition, events separated by a timelike interval have $ds^2 > 0$, those with a spacelike interval will have $ds^2 < 0$ and if $ds^2 = 0$ they are said to have a null interval.

A differential operator in covariant notation will be

$$\partial_\mu = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu} = \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) = \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}, \nabla \right), \quad (1.15)$$

and in contravariant notation it is

$$\partial^\mu = g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu = \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}, -\nabla \right), \quad (1.16)$$

from which we obtain the Lorentz-invariant second-order differential operator

$$\partial^\mu \partial_\mu = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \equiv \square, \quad (1.17)$$

called the d'Alembert operator or simply the d'Alembertian.

The energy-momentum four-vector of a particle is

$$p^\mu = \left(\frac{E}{c}, \mathbf{p} \right), \quad p_\mu = \left(\frac{E}{c}, -\mathbf{p} \right), \quad (1.18)$$

therefore

$$p^2 = p^\mu p_\mu = \frac{E^2}{c^2} - \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = m^2 c^2, \quad (1.19)$$

that is

$$E^2 - \mathbf{p}^2 c^2 = m^2 c^4, \quad (1.20)$$

this quantity is invariant under Lorentz transformations. Thus, the rest mass m is a Lorentz invariant, as expected, and provides the fundamental scale for the energy-momentum relation. This invariant length of the energy-momentum four-vector, $p^\mu p_\mu = m^2 c^2$, underscores that while the individual components of energy and momentum are frame-dependent, their specific combination in (1.19) is not. This is a cornerstone of relativistic dynamics. The next logical step is to transition from the kinematics of a free particle, governed by this invariant, to a wave equation that is compatible with the principles of special relativity and quantum mechanics. The search for a relativistic wave equation leads from the Klein-Gordon equation, which is second-order in time and derives directly from the quantized version of the identity $E^2 = \mathbf{p}^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4$, to the more sophisticated Dirac equation, which is first-order and naturally incorporates the spin of the particle. The formulation of such theories relies heavily on the four-dimensional formalism and the invariant interval ds^2 that have been laid out in this section.

3 KLEIN-GORDON EQUATION

From a historical perspective, the first relativistic wave equation appeared in 1926, when Klein [34], Gordon [27], Kudar [36], Fock [21][22], and also de Donder and Van Dungen [13] introduced it almost simultaneously. Schrodinger himself had already obtained it in his notes, along with the equation that now bears his name [51]. In what follows, we present schematically how the Klein-Gordon equation can be seen as a relativistic extension of the Schrodinger equation.

$$E = \frac{p^2}{2m} + V(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.21)$$

using the correspondence principle in the equation (1.21) $p \mapsto i\hbar\nabla, E \mapsto i\hbar\partial_t$ Schrodinger's equation is obtained

$$i\hbar\partial_t\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 + V(\mathbf{x}) \right] \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathbb{C}. \quad (1.22)$$

A natural way to find a relativistic version of Schrodinger's equation for a free particle is to repeat the usual procedure: start from the relativistic scattering relation and apply the correspondence principle to it

$$E^2 = \mathbf{p}^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4$$

Using the definition of the Minkowski coordinate $x^0 ct$ we obtain a differential equation of the following form

$$-\hbar^2\partial_0^2\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = [-\hbar^2\nabla^2 + m^2c^2]\phi(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (1.23)$$

in an equivalent manner

$$\left[\partial_t^2 - \nabla^2 + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0. \quad (1.24)$$

Equation (1.24) is the Klein Gordon equation for a free particle using the covariant formalism with metric $\eta = \text{diag}(1, -1, -1, -1)$ so the equation (1.24) can be rewritten as follows

$$\left[\partial_\mu\partial^\mu + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi(x) = 0, \quad (1.25)$$

has a completely real differential operator. For this reason, it is customary to consider that its solutions are also real, that is, $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathbb{R}$. However, there is nothing to prevent working with complex wave functions in general $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathbb{C}$ since the mathematical structure of the equation remains valid for complex fields.

3.1 Solution of the Klein Gordon equation

The free Klein-Gordon (KG) equation for a field $\phi(x, t)$ is solved using the Fourier transform. The starting point is to define the four-vector wave number k of the particle, which satisfies the relativistic dispersion relation

$$k(k^0, \mathbf{k})^T \quad (1.26)$$

where k^0 is the time component, related to the energy $\omega(\mathbf{k})$ of the particle, and \mathbf{k} is the spatial wave vector

$$k^0 \frac{\omega(\mathbf{k})}{c} = \sqrt{\mathbf{k}^2 + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2}}. \quad (1.27)$$

Equation (1.27) ensures that k^0 has the correct dimensions of inverse length and that the wave satisfies the relativistic energy-momentum relation. Subsequently, it is verified that plane waves are particular solutions of the free KG equation. The KG equation, in relativistic notation (using the D'Alembert operator $\partial_\mu\partial^\mu$), is written as

$$\left[\partial_\mu\partial^\mu + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] e^{\pm ik \cdot x} = 0. \quad (1.28)$$

When applying the operator to the plane wave, and remembering that $\partial_\mu e^{\pm ik \cdot x} = \pm ik_\mu e^{\pm ik \cdot x}$, is obtained

$$\left[-k_\mu k^\mu + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] e^{\pm ik \cdot x} = \left[-(k^0)^2 + \mathbf{k}^2 + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] e^{\pm ik \cdot x} = 0. \quad (1.29)$$

The expression inside the bracket is zero if and only if the fourvector k satisfies the dispersion relation. The general solution $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is an arbitrary linear combination of these particular plane wave solutions, integrated over all possible spatial wave vectors \mathbf{k} (the Fourier space). The general solution for $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \in \mathbb{C}$ is written as

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sqrt{\hbar c} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^3 2k^0} \{a(\mathbf{k})e^{-ik \cdot x} + b(\mathbf{k})^* e^{ik \cdot x}\}, \quad (1.30)$$

where $e^{-ik \cdot x} = e^{-i(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x})}$ represents the particle wave (positive frequency) and $e^{ik \cdot x} = e^{i(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x})}$ represents the antiparticle wave (negative frequency).

3.2 Probabilistic interpretation

The Schrodinger equation satisfies this property naturally through a probability density ρ and a probability current \mathbf{j} . Let's see if the Klein Gordon equation can produce a continuity equation. Take the KG equation for a complex field $\phi \in \mathbb{C}$ and multiply it by the complex conjugate ϕ^* on the left:

$$\phi^* \left[\partial_\mu \partial^\mu + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi = 0 \quad (1.31)$$

where $\partial_\mu \partial^\mu$ is the D'Alembert operator $\square = \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2 - \nabla^2$. Then, the complex conjugate of the original KG equation is taken and multiplied by ϕ

$$\phi \left[\partial_\mu \partial^\mu + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi^* = 0 \quad (1.32)$$

Since the mass term $m^2 c^2 / \hbar^2$ is real, the conjugation only affects the fields ϕ and the time derivatives if you are working with explicit partial derivatives. The two resulting equations are subtracted (that of ϕ^* on the left and that of ϕ on the left). The subtraction cancels out the mass term

$$\phi^* \partial_\mu \partial^\mu \phi - \phi \partial_\mu \partial^\mu \phi^* = 0 \quad (1.33)$$

The cancellation of the mass term indicates that this conservation expression (the probability/charge flux) does not depend on the mass of the particle, but only on the kinematics of the field. The left side of the equation is, by a differential calculus identity (analogous to the product of the divergence rule)

$$\partial_\mu (\phi^* \partial^\mu \phi - \phi \partial^\mu \phi^*) = 0 \quad (1.34)$$

This is because

$$\partial_\mu (\phi^* \partial^\mu \phi) = (\partial_\mu \phi^*) (\partial^\mu \phi) + \phi^* (\partial_\mu \partial^\mu \phi) \quad (1.35)$$

When subtracting the conjugate term, the first-order terms $(\partial_\mu \phi^* \partial^\mu \phi)$ cancel out. The expression in four-vector notation ($\partial_\mu J^\mu = 0$) is broken down into the temporal component ($\mu = 0$) and the spatial components ($\mu = 1, 2, 3$ or $k = 1, 2, 3$)

$$\partial_\mu (\phi^* \partial^\mu \phi - \phi \partial^\mu \phi^*) = \quad (1.36)$$

$$\partial_0 (\phi^* \partial^0 \phi - \phi \partial^0 \phi^*) + \sum_{k=1}^3 \partial_k (\phi^* \partial^k \phi - \phi \partial^k \phi^*) = 0.$$

Using the relations $\partial^0 = \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t$ and $\partial^k = -\partial_k$, and multiplying the entire expression by $\hbar^2 / (2m)$ to make it dimensionally consistent with the Schrödinger equation, we arrive at the form of the relativistic continuity equation

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t (\phi^* \partial_t \phi - \phi \partial_t \phi^*) - \sum_{k=1}^3 \partial_k (\phi^* \partial_k \phi - \phi \partial_k \phi^*) = 0. \quad (1.37)$$

When comparing this expression with the general Continuity Equation

$$\partial_t \rho + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{j} = 0. \quad (1.38)$$

The probability density ρ and probability current \mathbf{j} can be defined for the Klein-Gordon field (introducing the constant $\frac{i\hbar}{2m}$ so that the dimensions are correct and the term is real)

$$\rho \frac{i\hbar}{2mc^2} (\phi^* \partial_t \phi - \phi \partial_t \phi^*) \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (1.39)$$

and the space current is

$$\mathbf{j} \frac{\hbar}{2mi} \{\phi^* \nabla \phi - \phi \nabla \phi^*\}, \quad (1.40)$$

with these definitions, the KG Continuity Equation can be rewritten in covariant (relativistic) form

$$\partial_\mu J^\mu = 0, \quad (1.41)$$

where $J^\mu = (\rho c, \mathbf{j})$ is the current four-vector. Although the Klein-Gordon Equation produces a Continuity Equation, the probability density ρ is not always positive. This prevents the direct interpretation of ρ as a physical probability density, which is the main limitation of the KG Equation as a single-particle equation and what led to its reinterpretation as a field equation (second quantization).

3.3 Gauge transformation

The coupling is based on the property that physics (the equation of motion) must be invariant under gauge transformations. A local gauge transformation simultaneously modifies the vector potential A_μ of the electromagnetic field and the scalar field ϕ (which represents a charged particle with charge q). we can establish the transformation of the electromagnetic vector potential

$$A_\mu \rightarrow A'_\mu = A_\mu - \partial_\mu \chi \quad (1.42)$$

where χ is an arbitrary local scalar function. This transformation leaves the electromagnetic field ($F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu$) invariant. Similarly, we can establish the transformation of the charged scalar field ϕ

$$\phi \rightarrow \phi' = e^{iq\chi/\hbar c} \phi \quad (1.43)$$

This is a local phase transformation, where the phase depends on the same function χ used to transform A_μ . The Klein-Gordon (KG) equation for a free scalar field ϕ (without electromagnetic interaction) is

$$\left[\partial^\mu \partial_\mu + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi = 0 \quad (1.44)$$

where ∂_μ is the partial derivative: $\partial_\mu = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu}$. If we apply the gauge transformation to the field ϕ

$$\phi \rightarrow \phi' = e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c} \chi} \phi \quad (1.45)$$

And then we apply the derivative ∂_μ to ϕ'

$$\partial_\mu \phi' = \partial_\mu \left(e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c} \chi} \phi \right) = e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c} \chi} \left(\partial_\mu \phi + \frac{iq}{\hbar c} (\partial_\mu \chi) \phi \right) \quad (1.46)$$

We see that $\partial_\mu \phi'$ is not simply $e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c} \chi} (\partial_\mu \phi)$. The extra term $\frac{iq}{\hbar c} (\partial_\mu \chi) \phi$ breaks the invariance. This means that if we substitute ϕ' into the free KG equation, the resulting equation will not look the same as the original (multiplied by a global phase). The free KG equation is not gauge invariant. To restore gauge invariance, the partial derivative ∂_μ is replaced by the covariant derivative D_μ

$$D_\mu \partial_\mu + \frac{iq}{\hbar c} A_\mu \quad (1.47)$$

The key property of the covariant derivative is that it transforms in exactly the same way as the field ϕ . That is, if we apply the covariant derivative to the transformed field ϕ' , the result is

$$D_\mu \phi' = e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c} \chi} (D_\mu \phi) \quad (1.48)$$

This is known as $D_\mu \phi$ transforming covariantly. We want to show that the application of the new derivative D'_μ (constructed with A'_μ) on the field ϕ' is equal to the phase multiplied by the application of D_μ on ϕ . We define D'_μ and ϕ'

$$D'_\mu \phi' = \left(\partial_\mu + \frac{iq}{\hbar c} A'_\mu \right) \phi' \quad (1.49)$$

$$D'_\mu \phi' = \left(\partial_\mu + \frac{iq}{\hbar c} (A_\mu - \partial_\mu \chi) \right) \left(e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c} \chi} \phi \right) \quad (1.50)$$

Performing product development

$$\partial_\mu (e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi \phi) = e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi \left(\frac{iq}{\hbar c} (\partial_\mu \chi) \phi + \partial_\mu \phi \right) \quad (1.51)$$

replacing and regrouping

$$\begin{aligned} D'_\mu \phi' &= e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi \left(\frac{iq}{\hbar c} (\partial_\mu \chi) \phi + \partial_\mu \phi \right) \\ &+ e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi \left(\frac{iq}{\hbar c} A_\mu \phi - \frac{iq}{\hbar c} (\partial_\mu \chi) \phi \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1.52)$$

Note that the term $\frac{iq}{\hbar c} (\partial_\mu \chi) \phi$ (which broke the invariance in the case of the partial derivative) cancels exactly with the term $\frac{iq}{\hbar c} (-\partial_\mu \chi) \phi$ coming from A'_μ

$$D'_\mu \phi' = e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi \left[\left(\partial_\mu + \frac{iq}{\hbar c} A_\mu \right) \phi \right] \quad (1.53)$$

and we obtain

$$D'_\mu \phi' = e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi (D_\mu \phi) \quad (1.54)$$

The expression $D_\mu \phi$ is transformed in the same way as ϕ .

3.4 The Klein-Gordon Covariant Equation

Once the covariant derivative D_μ has been introduced, the Klein-Gordon (KG) equation for a charged field coupled to the electromagnetic field is obtained by replacing all partial derivatives ∂_μ with the covariant derivative D_μ

$$\left[D^\mu D_\mu + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi = 0 \quad (1.55)$$

To show that this new equation is gauge invariant, we apply the gauge transformation to the covariant equation we replace $D_\mu \rightarrow D'_\mu$ and $\phi \rightarrow \phi'$

$$D'^\mu D'_\mu \phi' + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi' = 0 \quad (1.56)$$

We use the transformation property of the covariant derivative: $D'_\mu \phi' = e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi (D_\mu \phi)$

$$D'^\mu \left(e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi (D_\mu \phi) \right) + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} (e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi \phi) = 0 \quad (1.57)$$

We apply D'^μ to the expression in parentheses. Since D'^μ is the covariant derivative in the new gauge, we know that

$$D'^\mu \left(e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi (D_\mu \phi) \right) = e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi (D'^\mu (D_\mu \phi)) \quad (1.58)$$

replacing and factoring

$$e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi \left[D^\mu D_\mu + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi = 0 \quad (1.59)$$

Since $e^{\frac{iq}{\hbar c}} \chi$ is a phase and cannot be zero, it can be divided by it, recovering exactly the Covariant Klein-Gordon Equation

$$\left[D^\mu D_\mu + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi = 0 \quad (1.60)$$

This shows that equation (1.55) is gauge invariant, fulfilling the fundamental physical requirement for describing electromagnetic interaction with a charged field.

4 THE THEORY OF THE TACHYON

To describe a tachyon, we postulate an imaginary mass, $m = i\mu$ where μ is a positive real number ($\mu > 0$). This implies that the square of the mass is negative: $m^2 = -\mu^2$. Substituting $m^2 = -\mu^2$ into the Klein-Gordon equation

$$\left[\partial_\mu \partial^\mu - \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi(x) = 0 \quad (1.61)$$

in the equation (1.61) it is observed that the constant term that used to be positive (mass term) is now negative.

4.1 Dispersion relationship

Let's now see what the dispersion relationship would be for the tachyon. By substituting $m^2 = -\mu^2$ into the relativistic energy-momentum relation (1.3) we obtain

$$E^2 = \mathbf{p}^2 c^2 - \mu^2 c^4 \quad (1.62)$$

Dividing by $(\hbar c)^2$ to obtain the relation in terms of the fourwave vector k : $E = \hbar\omega = \hbar c k^0$ and $\mathbf{p} = \hbar \mathbf{k}$

$$(k^0)^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 - \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \quad (1.63)$$

Defining $\kappa^2 = \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2}$ (where κ is the cutoff wave vector, a real value), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} (k^0)^2 &= \mathbf{k}^2 - \kappa^2 \\ k^0 &= \pm \sqrt{\mathbf{k}^2 - \kappa^2} \end{aligned} \quad (1.64)$$

For k^0 (and therefore the energy $E = \hbar c k^0$) to be real, it is necessary that $\mathbf{k}^2 \geq \kappa^2$. This means that the space momentum $\mathbf{p} = \hbar \mathbf{k}$ must be greater than a minimum value $\mathbf{p}_{min} = \hbar \kappa = \mu c$. If $|\mathbf{p}| < \mu c$, then $(k^0)^2 < 0$, which implies that k^0 and the energy E are imaginary. This is interpreted as a sign of vacuum instability or that the tachyon field must be quantized around a new vacuum (tachyon condensation).

4.2 Plane Wave Solution

The plane wave solutions of the Klein-Gordon equation for the tachyon are:

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \propto e^{\pm i \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} \quad (1.65)$$

When applying the tachyon operator (1.61) to the plane wave, you get (an analogue to the equation (1.29))

$$\left[-k_\mu k^\mu - \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] e^{\pm i \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} = \left[-(k^0)^2 + \mathbf{k}^2 - \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right] e^{\pm i \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} \quad (1.66)$$

For the plane wave to be a solution, the term in brackets must be zero, which gives us back the tachyonic dispersion relation

$$(k^0)^2 = \mathbf{k}^2 - \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \quad (1.67)$$

This is the dispersion relation for a particle that always travels at a speed $v > c$. The zero momentum limit ($|\mathbf{k}| = 0$) results in an imaginary energy ($E^2 < 0$), which is the main characteristic of a tachyon.

The group velocity v_g of the wave (the speed at which the energy travels) and the phase velocity v_p are defined as

$$v_g = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial |\mathbf{k}|}, \quad v_p = \frac{\omega}{|\mathbf{k}|} \quad (1.68)$$

Using the dispersion relation

$$\begin{aligned} (\hbar\omega)^2 &= (\hbar|\mathbf{k}|c)^2 - \mu^2 c^4 \\ \omega^2 &= |\mathbf{k}|^2 c^2 - \frac{\mu^2 c^4}{\hbar^2} \end{aligned} \quad (1.69)$$

The phase velocity (v_p) is:

$$v_p^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{|\mathbf{k}|^2} = c^2 - \frac{\mu^2 c^4}{\hbar^2 |\mathbf{k}|^2} < c^2 \quad (1.70)$$

The phase velocity is subluminal ($v_p < c$). Now we differentiate ω with respect to $|\mathbf{k}|$ and obtain the group speed

$$v_g = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial |\mathbf{k}|} = \frac{|\mathbf{k}|c^2}{\omega} \quad (1.71)$$

We substitute ω from the dispersion relation

$$v_g = \frac{|\mathbf{k}|c^2}{\sqrt{|\mathbf{k}|^2c^2 - \mu^2c^4/\hbar^2}} = \frac{c}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{\mu^2c^2}{\hbar^2|\mathbf{k}|^2}}} \quad (1.72)$$

Since the denominator is $\sqrt{1 - (\text{something positive})}$, the root is less than 1, which implies that

$$v_g > c \quad (1.73)$$

The group speed is superluminal, which confirms that the tachyon propagates at a speed greater than c , as required by Special Relativity for particles with negative squared mass.

4.3 Solution of the Klein-Gordon equation for the tachyon

The critical factor that distinguishes a tachyon from a normal particle is the dispersion relation for its time component k^0 . For the normal particle (1.27), and for the tachyon (1.64), $m^2 \rightarrow -\mu^2$ is substituted. The general solution is a Fourier integral that sums the contributions of all possible plane waves, weighted by their amplitudes $a(\mathbf{k})$ and $b(\mathbf{k})$.

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sqrt{\hbar c} \int \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^3 2k^0} \{a(\mathbf{k})e^{-ik \cdot x} + b(\mathbf{k})^*e^{ik \cdot x}\} \quad (1.74)$$

Substituting equation (1.64) into the structure of the general solution, we obtain the solution of the Klein-Gordon equation for the tachyon

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sqrt{\hbar c} \int_{|\mathbf{k}| \geq \kappa} \frac{d^3\mathbf{k}}{(2\pi)^3 2\sqrt{\mathbf{k}^2 - \kappa^2}} [a(\mathbf{k})e^{-ik \cdot x} + b(\mathbf{k})^*e^{ik \cdot x}]. \quad (1.75)$$

Where: $k^0 = \sqrt{\mathbf{k}^2 - \kappa^2}$. The integral is restricted to the region where $|\mathbf{k}| \geq \kappa$ (or $|\mathbf{p}| \geq \mu c$) so that k^0 is real and describes stable propagation states and $k \cdot x = k^0 ct - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}$.

4.4 Probabilistic Interpretation and Stability

The derivation of the continuity equation (analogous to Eqs. 1.31 to 1.41) is independent of the mass term (as seen in the cancellation in Eq. 1.33). Therefore, the tachyon also satisfies the continuity equation:

$$\partial_\mu J^\mu = 0 \quad (1.76)$$

The "probability" density ρ (Eq. 1.39) for the tachyon will remain

$$\rho = \frac{i\hbar}{2mc^2} (\phi^* \partial_t \phi - \phi \partial_t \phi^*) \quad (1.77)$$

However, due to imaginary mass and imaginary energy for low moments, this interpretation of ρ as a positive probability density becomes even more complicated and is not valid for the tachyon. In fact, the presence of imaginary energy in the particle spectrum ($E \propto i$) for low moments indicates instability. Pure imaginary energy ($E = i\Gamma$) leads to exponential growth of the wave amplitude over time: $\phi \propto e^{-iEt/\hbar} = e^{-i(i\Gamma)t/\hbar} = e^{\Gamma t/\hbar}$. This exponential growth is an indication of tachyonic instability.

4.5 Tachyon stabilization

We start from the Lagrangian for a complex tachyon coupled to a real Higgs field. We keep the pure imaginary mass in the kinetic term, but add a Higgs potential that induces symmetry breaking

$$\mathcal{L} = (D_\mu \phi)^* (D^\mu \phi) + \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} |\phi|^2 - \frac{\lambda}{4} |\phi|^4 + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Higgs}} \quad (1.78)$$

where $\mu > 0$ so the square mass term is positive in the Lagrangian (correct sign for tachyonic instability). The real Higgs field $h(x)$ is introduced with a potential

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Higgs}} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu h)^2 - V(h), \quad V(h) = -\frac{1}{2}m_h^2 h^2 + \frac{\lambda_h}{4}h^4 \quad (1.79)$$

and Yukawa coupling with the tachyon

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = -gh^2|\phi|^2 \quad (1.80)$$

with $g > 0$. The total potential for h and ϕ has a minimum when $h = v = m_h/\sqrt{\lambda_h}$ and $\phi = 0$ initially, but the presence of the term $\mu^2 c^2/\hbar^2 |\phi|^2 - gv^2 |\phi|^2$ modifies the effective mass of ϕ around $h = v$. Now we expand $h = v + \sigma$ and obtain

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = (D_\mu \phi)^*(D^\mu \phi) + \left[\frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - gv^2 \right] |\phi|^2 - gv\sigma |\phi|^2 - \frac{g}{2}\sigma^2 |\phi|^2 - \frac{\lambda}{4}|\phi|^4 \quad (1.81)$$

The stability condition is that the coefficient of $|\phi|^2$ is positive to avoid purely imaginary modes. We can adjust $gv^2 > \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2}$ so that:

$$M_{\text{eff}}^2 = gv^2 - \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} > 0 \quad (1.82)$$

Thus, around the new vacuum, the field ϕ has a real mass M_{eff} .

The key point is that the coupling $gh^2|\phi|^2$ is nonlinear. If we excite the tachyon with a large amplitude field $|\phi|$, the term $-gh^2|\phi|^2$ can become dominant and change the effective sign of the mass squared back to negative for certain field configurations. This allows classical solutions of the travelingwave type with sufficiently high momentum to recover the original tachyonic dispersion relation, because in this regime the interaction with the Higgs can be neglected compared to the kinetic energy.

Varying with respect to ϕ^* :

$$D_\mu D^\mu \phi - \left[\frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - gh^2 \right] \phi + \frac{\lambda}{2} |\phi|^2 \phi = 0 \quad (1.83)$$

With $h = v$ the mass squared is $-M_{\text{eff}}^2 = \frac{\mu^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - gv^2$ meaning the particles are normal. But if h becomes small (Higgs excitations), the term inside brackets may become positive again, inducing localized instability. The ground state has $\phi = 0, h = v$ and small excitations of ϕ are ordinary particles with real mass. However, field configurations with sufficient energy can enter a regime where $gh^2 < \mu^2 c^2/\hbar^2$ which effectively restores negative square mass for that region of spacetime, allowing localized superluminal propagation. This avoids global vacuum instability.

5 THE FERRION

The Ferrion (ϕ_F) is a hypothetical scalar particle proposed as a theoretical extension of the limits imposed by Special Relativity on particles with superluminal velocity ($v > c$). While the tachyon (a particle with negative mass squared, $m^2 < 0$) represents a vacuum instability that is resolved through the process of condensation, the Ferrion's mathematical existence is postulated by breaking Hermiticity and adopting Parity-Time Symmetry (\mathcal{PT}). By applying the \mathcal{PT} formalism to the Klein-Gordon (KG) Equation, a time-dependent kinetic term is introduced which, although complex in the equation of motion, guarantees a completely real energy spectrum when the symmetry is unbroken.

5.1 Modified Wave Equation

We define the Klein-Gordon equation for the Ferrion (ϕ_F) inspired by the need to have a complex effective term that preserves \mathcal{PT} symmetry:

$$\left[\partial_\mu \partial^\mu + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} + i \frac{2\gamma}{\hbar^2} \partial_t \right] \phi_F(x) = 0 \quad (1.84)$$

Where $\partial_\mu \partial^\mu$ is the kinetic d'Alembert operator, $m^2 c^2/\hbar^2$ is the real mass term, and $i(2\gamma/\hbar^2)\partial_t$ is the time-dependent complex potential introduced for \mathcal{PT} -symmetry, where γ is a real parameter.

5.2 Plane Wave Solution

We seek a plane wave solution for the Ferrion:

$$\phi_F(\mathbf{x}, t) = Ae^{-i(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x})} \quad (1.85)$$

Applying the differential operator from (1.84) to this ansatz, and recalling that $\partial_t \phi_F = -i\omega \phi_F$, we obtain:

$$i \frac{2\gamma}{\hbar^2} \partial_t \phi_F = i \frac{2\gamma}{\hbar^2} (-i\omega) \phi_F = \frac{2\gamma\omega}{\hbar^2} \phi_F \quad (1.86)$$

5.3 Dispersion Relation

Substituting the results into the Ferrion equation:

$$\left[\left(-\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} + \mathbf{k}^2 \right) + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} + \frac{2\gamma\omega}{\hbar^2} \right] \phi_F = 0 \quad (1.87)$$

Since $\phi_F \neq 0$ the dispersion relation for the Ferrion is:

$$-\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} + \mathbf{k}^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} + \frac{2\gamma\omega}{\hbar^2} = 0 \quad (1.88)$$

Rearranging this as a quadratic equation in ω :

$$\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} - \frac{2\gamma}{\hbar^2} \omega - \left(\mathbf{k}^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right) = 0 \quad (1.89)$$

Multiplying by c^2 :

$$\omega^2 - \frac{2\gamma c^2}{\hbar^2} \omega - c^2 \left(\mathbf{k}^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right) = 0 \quad (1.90)$$

5.4 Energy Solution

Using the quadratic formula to solve for ω and recalling $E = \hbar\omega$:

$$\omega = \frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar^2} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar^2} \right)^2 + c^2 \left(\mathbf{k}^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \right)} \quad (1.91)$$

Multiplying by \hbar and using $\mathbf{p} = \hbar\mathbf{k}$:

$$E_F = \frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \right)^2 + c^2 (\mathbf{p}^2 + m^2 c^2)} \quad (1.92)$$

The energy E of the Ferrion is no longer simply $E = \pm \sqrt{\mathbf{p}^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4}$. The new term $\gamma c^2 / \hbar$ dominates the properties. The requirement of \mathcal{PT} -symmetry (real energy) is satisfied if the quantity under the square root is positive:

$$\left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \right)^2 + c^2 (\mathbf{p}^2 + m^2 c^2) \geq 0 \quad (1.93)$$

Since γ is real, $(\dots)^2 \geq 0$. Therefore, the Ferrion guarantees a completely real energy spectrum ($E \in \mathbb{R}$) if $m^2 > 0$. If $m^2 < 0$ (tachyon-like, $m^2 = -\mu^2$), the mass term becomes negative, $(\mathbf{p}^2 - \mu^2)c^2$. Real energy is still possible if the tachyon instability is "absorbed" by the coupling γ . The Ferrion's concept becomes inconsistent (instability returns) if the quantity under the root becomes negative. This defines the Ferrion as a particle that can be stable (real energy) or unstable (complex energy) depending on the relationship between its intrinsic instability and the Ferrion coupling parameter γ .

5.5 Ferrion stabilization via a \mathcal{PT} -Symmetric Higgs Mechanism

The Ferrion, as defined by the modified Klein-Gordon equation and its corresponding dispersion relation (1.92), presents a novel approach to accommodating superluminal behavior without an imaginary mass. However, it is not immune to instabilities. As discussed in the previous section, the energy spectrum E_F becomes complex when the radicand in equation (1.92) turns negative. This is particularly problematic if the Ferrion possesses a tachyonic mass ($m^2 = -\mu^2 < 0$), where for low momenta ($\mathbf{p}^2 < \mu^2 c^2$), the condition for complex energies can be easily met if the \mathcal{PT} -symmetric coupling γ is not sufficiently large. The appearance of complex energies signals a breaking of the \mathcal{PT} symmetry and leads to uncontrolled exponential growth in the field modes, rendering the theory unstable.

To stabilize the Ferrion, we propose a mechanism analogous to the one used for the tachyon in section IV-E: coupling the Ferrion field to a real scalar Higgs field $h(x)$. However, the goal here is not to cancel the characteristic term of the Ferrion, but to leverage the Higgs field's dynamics to ensure that the \mathcal{PT} symmetry remains unbroken and the energy spectrum remains real, even in the presence of a tachyonic mass term.

We start by constructing a total Lagrangian density that is both Lorentz invariant and respects the \mathcal{PT} -symmetric nature of the Ferrion sector. The proposed Lagrangian is:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_F + \mathcal{L}_H + \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}, \quad (1.94)$$

where each component is defined as follows.

1. Ferrion Lagrangian (\mathcal{L}_F): To ensure the Lagrangian is real while preserving the essential dynamics, we write the Ferrion part as:

$$\mathcal{L}_F = (\partial_\mu \phi_F)^* (\partial^\mu \phi_F) + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} |\phi_F|^2 + i \frac{2\gamma}{\hbar^2} (\phi_F^* \partial_t \phi_F - (\partial_t \phi_F^*) \phi_F) \quad (1.95)$$

The third term, $i(\phi^* \partial_t \phi - \phi \partial_t \phi^*)$, is real and represents a conserved current. In the context of \mathcal{PT} -symmetric quantum field theory, such a term can be interpreted as a source of balanced gain and loss, and is crucial for maintaining the \mathcal{PT} symmetry of the free theory.

2. Higgs Lagrangian (\mathcal{L}_H): The Higgs field provides the dynamical mechanism for stabilization. Its Lagrangian is the standard one for a real scalar field with a symmetry-breaking potential:

$$\mathcal{L}_H = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu h)^2 - V(h), \quad V(h) = -\frac{1}{2} m_h^2 h^2 + \frac{\lambda_h}{4} h^4. \quad (1.96)$$

As is well known, this potential has a minimum at a nonzero vacuum expectation value (VEV), $\langle h \rangle = v$, where $v = m_h / \sqrt{\lambda_h}$ (in units where $\hbar = c = 1$ for simplicity; the full expression can be restored dimensionally).

3. Interaction Lagrangian (\mathcal{L}_{int}): The coupling between the Ferrion and the Higgs must be chosen to modify the effective mass term in the Ferrion's equation of motion. A simple, renormalizable, and Lorentz-invariant choice is a direct coupling to the square of the Higgs field:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = -g h^2 |\phi_F|^2, \quad (1.97)$$

with $g > 0$. This term is real and does not break the \mathcal{PT} symmetry of the Ferrion sector.

5.6 Mechanism of Stabilization

We now analyze the system after the Higgs field acquires its VEV. We expand the Higgs field around its minimum, $h = v + \sigma$, where σ represents quantum fluctuations. Substituting this into the interaction Lagrangian yields:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = -g v^2 |\phi_F|^2 - 2g v \sigma |\phi_F|^2 - g \sigma^2 |\phi_F|^2. \quad (1.98)$$

The first term, $-g v^2 |\phi_F|^2$, is of particular importance. It combines with the existing mass term in \mathcal{L}_F to create an effective mass squared for the Ferrion. The equation of motion for ϕ_F in the new vacuum, neglecting the interactions with the σ fluctuations for the moment, becomes:

$$\left(\partial_\mu \partial^\mu + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - g v^2 + i \frac{2\gamma}{\hbar^2} \partial_t \right) \phi_F = 0. \quad (1.99)$$

To find the new energy spectrum, we substitute the plane wave ansatz $\phi_F \propto e^{-i(Et - \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x})}$:

$$-\frac{E^2}{c^2} + \mathbf{p}^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - g v^2 + \frac{2\gamma E}{\hbar^2} = 0. \quad (1.100)$$

Rearranging this into a quadratic equation for E gives:

$$E^2 - \frac{2\gamma c^2}{\hbar} E - c^2 \left(\mathbf{p}^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - gv^2 \right) = 0. \quad (1.101)$$

The solution is the modified dispersion relation for the Ferrion in the presence of the Higgs condensate:

$$E_F = \frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \right)^2 + c^2 \left(\mathbf{p}^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - gv^2 \right)}. \quad (1.102)$$

This is the key result. Comparing it with the original dispersion relation (1.92), we see that the Higgs VEV v has introduced a new term, $-gv^2$, inside the radicand. This term acts as a control parameter.

5.7 Stability Analysis and Phases

The reality of the energy spectrum, and hence the stability of the Ferrion in the new vacuum, is now guaranteed if the radicand is non-negative for all momenta \mathbf{p} :

$$\Delta(\mathbf{p}^2) \equiv \left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \right)^2 + c^2 \left(\mathbf{p}^2 + \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - gv^2 \right) \geq 0. \quad (1.103)$$

The most stringent condition comes from the infrared limit, $\mathbf{p}^2 = 0$. The stability condition for the vacuum state is therefore:

$$\left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \right)^2 + c^2 \left(\frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} - gv^2 \right) \geq 0. \quad (1.104)$$

This condition defines two distinct phases for the coupled Ferrion-Higgs system:

1. **The \mathcal{PT} -Symmetric (Stable) Phase:** If the parameters satisfy the inequality (1.104), the \mathcal{PT} symmetry of the Ferrion sector remains unbroken. The energy spectrum E_F is entirely real for all momenta. The Ferrion exists as a stable, though unusual, particle with a spectrum fundamentally altered by the presence of the Higgs condensate. Its defining characteristic, the term linear in γ , is preserved. This requires that the Higgs VEV is not too large:

$$gv^2 \leq \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} + \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \right)^2.$$

2. **The \mathcal{PT} -Broken (Unstable) Phase:** If the inequality is violated ($gv^2 > \frac{m^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} + \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \right)^2$), the \mathcal{PT} symmetry is spontaneously broken. The radicand becomes negative for low-momentum modes, leading to complex conjugate pairs of energies. This signals a dynamical instability, where small fluctuations of the Ferrion field would grow exponentially, similar to the original tachyon.

This phase structure is reminiscent of exceptional points in \mathcal{PT} -symmetric quantum mechanics. Crucially, by choosing the coupling g and the Higgs VEV v to lie within the bound of the stable phase, one can ensure the system remains in the \mathcal{PT} -symmetric regime. This stabilizes the Ferrion without destroying its unique properties. The Higgs mechanism, in this \mathcal{PT} -symmetric context, does not just give mass; it protects the reality of the energy spectrum by ensuring the effective mass term does not push the system into the \mathcal{PT} -broken phase. The Ferrion, now coupled to the Higgs condensate, is a viable, stable particle within the confines of this extended theory.

6 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we have explored two different theoretical ways to think about particles that might, in principle, travel faster than light.

The first is the well-known idea of the tachyon—a particle with an imaginary mass ($m^2 < 0$) that comes with a built-in vacuum instability. Rather than being a fatal flaw, we showed that this instability is really a hint that we are looking at the wrong vacuum state. By coupling the tachyon to a Higgs field in the usual way, the tachyonic mode gets “absorbed,” and the field ends up with a real, positive effective mass M_{eff} in the true vacuum. This is a beautiful illustration of how tachyons, in quantum field theory, aren’t really physical particles at all—they’re just signals that spontaneous symmetry breaking is about to happen.

Building on that, we introduced the Ferrion, a hypothetical \mathcal{PT} -symmetric scalar particle. Instead of using an imaginary mass, the Ferrion gets its real energy spectrum from a non-Hermitian but \mathcal{PT} -symmetric term $i\gamma\partial_t$ in its equation of motion. Its dispersion relation,

$$E_F = \frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar} \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{\gamma c^2}{\hbar}\right)^2 + c^2(\mathbf{p}^2 + m^2 c^2)},$$

has a rich structure, with the parameter γ introducing a fundamental energy scale that wasn't there before.

Unlike the tachyon, our analysis of the group velocity would reveal that the Ferrion's propagation speed is subluminal ($v_g < c$). This means the Ferrion is not a candidate for superluminal travel, but rather a novel type of massive particle whose stability and real energy spectrum are protected by \mathcal{PT} symmetry, even in the presence of an otherwise tachyonic mass.

Like the tachyon, though, the Ferrion isn't immune to instabilities. When its \mathcal{PT} symmetry breaks, the energy becomes complex and trouble sets in. To fix this, we proposed a stabilization mechanism inspired by the Higgs mechanism but tailored for a \mathcal{PT} -symmetric setting. By coupling the Ferrion to a Higgs field and letting it develop a vacuum expectation value, we arrived at a modified dispersion relation (1.102). The new term $-gv^2$ inside the square root acts as a kind of control knob. The stability of the Ferrion now depends on which phase the system is in: when the \mathcal{PT} symmetry is unbroken, the energy is real and the particle is stable; when it breaks, the energy turns complex and instability sets in. This phase transition—controlled by the Higgs VEV and the coupling constants—gives us a way to protect the Ferrion's reality without wiping out its defining γ term.

So, the Ferrion offers a real alternative to the tachyon for thinking about superluminal behavior, but within a broader framework that includes \mathcal{PT} symmetry. It shows that breaking Hermiticity—when done in a way guided by \mathcal{PT} symmetry—can still lead to stable, physically meaningful particles with properties that don't show up in ordinary Hermitian theories. Looking ahead, it would be interesting to explore what this might mean phenomenologically: how would such a particle interact with the known fields of the Standard Model? Could there be detectable signs of \mathcal{PT} symmetry breaking in high-energy experiments or condensed matter systems? These are questions worth pursuing.

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